

Form of consent ('Informed Consent') for collection and processing personal interview data

Research project:

Institution carrying out the research:

Project management:

Interviewer / interviewers:

Interview date:

Description of the research project (please tick where applicable):

- oral explanation
- written explanation

The interviews are recorded on a recording device and then written down in text by members of the research project. For further scientific evaluation of the interview, texts including all information that leads to a identification of the person will be changed.

Personal contact details are separated from interview data and are secured inaccessibly to third parties. Once the research project has been completed, your contact details will automatically be deleted, unless you agree explicitly to further storage as a contact option for subject-related research projects. Of course you can object to longer storage at any time.

The participation in the interviews is voluntary. You have the option at any time to stop the interviews any time, refuse further interviews and withdraw your agreement to a recording and transcript of the interview (s) without having any disadvantages.

- yes
- no

I agree to be contacted for future related research projects. For this purpose, my contact details will be kept savely beyond the end of the research project.

- yes
- no

First name ; Surname in capital letters
